

LEXICAL CORRESPONDENCE ISSUES IN UZBEK-ENGLISH TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Abstract:

This paper explores the complexities of lexical correspondence in the translation process between English and Uzbek. It highlights the identification of lexical equivalents for words, emphasizing the importance of distinguishing between different types of semantic connections. The three main categories discussed include full lexical correspondence, partial or variant lexical correspondence, and lack of correspondence. The article provides illustrative examples, highlighting the challenges translators face in selecting appropriate translations based on context, especially when dealing with words with multiple meanings. The paper underscores the significance of considering the entire text and context in achieving lexical compatibility. Additionally, it emphasizes the role of both bilingual and explanatory dictionaries in aiding the translator in finding precise meanings for words in the translation process.

Key words: Lexical correspondence, full correspondence, context-independent, partial match, context-bound, multiple meanings.

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Introduction. During the process of translation, it is essential to identify lexical equivalents for words in the original language within the target language. When viewed from the perspective of English and Uzbek, English contains numerous words with multiple meanings, necessitating the translator to identify and utilize the appropriate translations in Uzbek. In translation theory, the act of finding lexically accurate words is referred to as lexical correspondence.

To accurately determine lexical compatibility, it is imperative to distinguish between various types of semantic connections among words. These types encompass:

1. Full lexical correspondence;
2. Partial or variant lexical correspondence;
3. Lack of correspondence [Слепович, 2014:13].

Main Part. We shall now explore these categories with the aid of illustrative examples. In the first category, full lexical correspondence, the meanings of words in both languages align perfectly. Regardless of the context, the meaning of the English word remains consistent in the translation, referred to as an alternative or equivalent. Prominent translation scholar V.N. Komissarov designates such words as context-independent [Комиссаров, 1990:71]. Approximately 30% of vocabulary consists of such words, including proper nouns, numbers, days of the week, months, many scientific and technical terms, geographical names, and other words. For instance, Canada, twelve, Tuesday, July, tractor, inflation, the Netherlands, etc.

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The second type of lexical compatibility is more prevalent than the others, and the primary reason for this lies in the extensive presence of words with similar meanings across various languages, including English and Uzbek. When an English word shares the same meaning as multiple words in the target language, it is considered a variant or a partial match [Раҳимов 2016: 90].

V.N. Komissarov refers to such words as context-bound. This represents a highly common form of meaningful interconnection between words [Комиссаров, 1990:75].

Within the translation process, the task of selecting the appropriate option is sufficiently challenging, and the translator must consider the role of context, specifically the sentence in which the word is situated within the text.

As evidence of our perspective, we can illustrate the word “variability” in English by examining its diverse translations into Uzbek when it is encountered in the text:

Table 1. The word “variability” in English and its diverse translations into Uzbek

English word: variability	Uzbek translation:
1. <i>variability of temper</i>	<i>kayfiyatning o'zgaruvchanligi</i>
2. <i>data variability</i>	<i>ma'lumotlarning xilma-xilligi</i>
3. <i>variability of prices</i>	<i>noturg'un narxlar</i>

A similar situation is observed in the translation of the words “house” and “table” into Uzbek. This is due to the fact that the word “house” can be translated as “uy” or “palata” in Uzbek, while the word “table” can be translated as “stol” or “jadval”.

Sometimes, an English-Uzbek dictionary provides multiple meanings for a word, and selecting the correct primary meaning of the word from the dictionary often leads to letter-for-letter translation (literalism or word-for-word translation), resulting in an awkward Uzbek translation.

For example: In the sentence, “I am happy to be involved in this project”, the word “involve” has seven different meanings, which are as follows:

1. *Iborat bo'lmoq;*
2. *Qorishtirmoq;*
3. *Ta'sir qilmoq;*
4. *Bog'liq bo'lmoq;*
5. *Taqozo etmoq;*
6. *Murakkab bo'lmoq;*
7. *Jalb etilmoq*

In the translation of this sentence, only the seventh meaning, “jalb etilmoq” (to be involved), fits correctly. The translation of the above sentence is as follows:

- *Men bu loyihada qatnashganimdan xursandman.*

However, the dictionary doesn't provide the meaning “qatnashmoq” for “to be involved”.

This situation indicates that, during the translation process, it is sometimes necessary to depart from the literal meanings of words to preserve language norms or to ensure the translator's communication is clear and concise.

A similar example can be seen with the word “ambitious”. It has multiple meanings, such as 1) *shuhratparast*; 2) *orzumand*; 3) *chanqoq*; 4) *jimjimador* in Uzbek. However, in order to provide an adequate translation for the sentence “The government is determined to implement its ambitious plans,” we should translate it as follows:

- *Hukumat o'zining ulug'vor rejalarni hayotga tadbiiq qilish niyatida.*

In this case, the word “ambitious” does not carry the meaning “ulug'vor” as per the dictionary. Undoubtedly, many words in the English language, like “ambitious”, have multiple meanings, each of which may correspond to entirely different meanings in the Uzbek language.

To translate a word with multiple meanings, it is necessary to find the appropriate meaning first, and then within that meaning's context, a suitable equivalent is sought. For example, in the two-volume “Новый большой англо-русский словарь” published under the editorship of Апресян Y.D., the word “rate” is presented with 14 different meanings [Апресян, 1994:28]. Each of these meanings contains its own range of possible equivalents, providing further specific options.

For instance, the second meaning of “rate” has the following variations in Uzbek:

1) *Maosh, ta'rif, haq*; 2) *Moliya, kurs*; 3) *Narx, qiymat*; 4) *Yuk tarifi*;

To translate a text related to a specific field, it is recommended to use specialized dictionaries. In A.V. Anikina's editorial “English-Russian Dictionary for Economics and Finance”, the word “rate” is explained on seven pages, accompanied by dozens of word combinations [АНИКИН 1993:398].

When translating such a situation from Uzbek to English, it is noticeable. In other words, a single Uzbek word may correspond to several words in English:

Table 2. *Lexical Correspondence: One Uzbek Word, Multiple English Equivalents*

Uzbek word: ochmoq	Uzbek word: retsept
- open (<i>kitobni</i>)	- prescription (<i>Meditzinada</i>)
- discover (<i>yangi yerni</i>)	- recipe (<i>oshxona</i>)
- reveal (<i>sirni</i>)	- formula
- unveal (<i>yodgorlikni</i>)	

One of the factors contributing to the occasional occurrence of partial word matches during the translation process is the existence of synonymous expressions within the vocabulary. The selection of synonyms in translation is contingent on the text's genre and style, as texts can take on various forms, be they artistic, informative, conversational, or poetic. For instance, in the English language, “dismiss” and “discharge” are employed in formal contexts, whereas “sack” and “fire” are part of conversational language [Слепович 2014” 14].

dismiss, discharge (bookish). He was discharged. U ishdan bo'shatildi.

sack, fire (colloquial) I am fired. Men ishdan bo'shatildim.

In language, words are used differently in various contexts and in relation to different subjects. For example, in the Uzbek language, the words “suzmoq”, “rassom”, and “mos kelmoq” can each correspond to three different words in English:

Table 3. *Cross-Linguistic Word Variations in Context*

Uzbek word: suzmoq
- swim (<i>kishiga, jonli mavjudotlarga</i>) Anvar is swimming in the river.
- sail (<i>qayiq va kemalarga</i>) The Titanic sailed only once.
- float (<i>bulutga yoki suvdagi cho'pga nisbatan</i>).The bottle is floating in the water.

In practical foreign language learning, government - relationship between a word and its dependents is one of the challenging aspects. In the following situations, we can be confident that a single word in Uzbek may have a different expression in English:

artmoq

wipe – artmoq (*terni, ko'z yoshni va h.*), o'chirmoq;

dust – changni artmoq;

The specific feature of words combining with each other varies in different languages and partly highlights the challenge of translation. For instance, in

Uzbek, the phrase “qattiq boshi og‘rimoq” is expressed in English using the phrase “have a bad headache” (not “a hard headache”).

It’s worth noting that in English, the verb “qilmoq, bajarmoq” is primarily expressed through the verb “to do”. However, the phrase “xato qilmoq” should be translated using the verb “to make”: “xato qilmoq” - to make a mistake.

Qo‘pol xato qilmoq – to make a bad mistake

As a result of the historical development, formation, and evolution of language, certain phrases have become conventional for various situations:

Wet paint! – Ehtiyot bo‘ling, bo‘yalgan!

Conclusion. It’s important to emphasize that, in the translation process, a significant number of words with broad meanings necessitate the task of selecting the most suitable translation equivalent in the target language. From a lexical perspective, ensuring their compatibility is vital, and the significance of the entire text and context is paramount, as demonstrated by the examples above.

Furthermore, not only bilingual dictionaries but also explanatory dictionaries play a crucial role in providing precise meanings for words that appear in two languages.

References:

- [1]. Bakiyev, F. J. (2023). *Translation strategy as a basic concept of translating subtitles*. *Golden Brain*, 1(15), 220-223.
- [2]. Faxriddin, B. J. (2023). *The concept of “Subtitles” and their working in the text*. *Golden Brain*, 1(15), 215-219.
- [3]. Salieva, Zarrina Ilkhomovna, et al. "Teaching Translation with a Moodle Database Activity: A Case-Study for Uzbek Undergraduate Students." *Nveo-Natural Volatiles & Essential Oils Journal | NVEO* (2021): 9127-9135.
- [4]. Аникин А.В. *Англо-русский словарь по экономике и финансам*. М.: Экономическая школа, 1993. — 590 с.
- [5]. Апресян Ю.Д. (общее руководство). *Новый Большой англо-русский словарь в трех томах. Том 3 R-Z*. М.: Русский язык, 1994. — 832 с.
- [6]. Комиссаров В.Н., Коралова А.Л. *Практикум по переводу с английского языка на русский. Учебное пособие для институтов и факультетов иностранных языков*. — М.: Высшая школа, 1990. — 127 с.
- [7]. Раҳимов Г.Х. *Таржима назарияси ва амалиёти*. Дарслик-мажмуа. — Т.: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» Давлат илмий нашриёти, 2016. — 176 б.
- [8]. Слепович В.С. *Курс перевода (английский - русский язык). Учебник для студентов ВУЗов по спец. "Мировая экономика"*. — 10-е изд. — Минск: ТетраСистемс, 2014. — 320 с.